

Overview of a kinaesthetic hand exoskeleton system

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Abstract—Within the new industrial era, the interaction between humans and virtual reality is spreading across our lives. The development of exoskeleton designed to enhance the immersivity of virtual reality environments has a potentially considerable social impact and arises as a hot research topic. The presented mechatronic design process of a kinaesthetic hand exoskeleton system meant to reproduce proprioceptive stimuli coming from the interaction with a virtual reality. The presented prototype is a modular device, equipped with force and pose sensors, and driven by a Bowden-cable-based remote actuation system. Unlike similar devices, the proposed exoskeleton is specifically thought for VR interaction and is designed to be reversible while exerting up to 15 N per finger.

Index Terms—Hand Exoskeleton System, kinaesthetic haptics, wearable robots, mechatronic design.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of the so-called *Industry 4.0* has revolutionized the industry's traditional concept by introducing a new attitude, based on automation and data exchange, which has brought a new perspective on Human-Machine Interaction (HMI). Humans and robots can now work together, safely, side by side, and even cooperate. In this context, Virtual Reality (VR) is rapidly emerging as one of the primary tools to provide augmented HMIs. The current trends in VR technologies focus mostly on providing immersive visual information, often lacking a proper haptic feedback; essential for achieving vivid experiences. As a result, the demand for VR-integrated devices that can physically replicate user interactions with the virtual environment has increased, making haptics a hot research topic.

Haptic devices can be classified according to the types of perception receptors they stimulate: cutaneous devices (tactile) and kinaesthetic devices (force/position) [3].

Exoskeletons have originated a considerable fascination in researchers as force delivery and kinaesthetic systems. These devices, being wearable, allow for a more authentic replication of actions within the VR and, besides, leave the users with a great freedom of movements, resulting in an incredibly immersive experience. However, finding a fair balance between VR rendering capability, the wearability of the resulting system, and the high performance required remains, to date, a stimulating challenge.

Achieving such a demanding tradeoff becomes even more complicated when it comes to designing Hand Exoskeleton

Systems (HESs) due to the complex limb anatomy, the minimal space, the high number of degrees of freedom (DOFs), and the articulated kinematics.

Despite the adversity, the authors presented a new mechatronic design of a kinaesthetic HES (see Figure 1) actuated by means of a Bowden-cable-based Remote Actuation System (RAS) to replicate force references elaborated within a VR environment on the user's fingers improving the user's sensorimotor and proprioceptive functions. The authors truly believe that systems like the one proposed here have the potential to play a crucial role in the advancement of entertainment and training platforms, as well as, in the development of innovative tele-rehabilitation devices and protocols.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The mechanical hardware that makes up the presented prototype can be divided mainly into the wearable part of the system, consisting of HE and the Bowden-cable-based RAS.

A. HE overview

The device under consideration can be identified as a rigid, bidirectional HES; as shown in Figure 1. These two keywords mean that this device present a rigid kinematics chain that can actively actuate both opening and closing of the fingers. Besides, the HE have been designed following the single-phalanx approach, which takes advantage of a single interaction point. In our case this point is located on the upper middle phalanx; the most suitable position to perform both fine movements and power grasps [1]. The kinematic chain presents a single DOF, and each component geometry is optimized on the user's anthropometric measurements through a customized algorithm [2].

The prototype embodies the actual implementation of just three finger modules: thumb, index, and middle finger; the minimum number of fingers that allows performing both force and precision grasps.

The architecture of the finger mechanism is meant to integrate a load cell (i.e., FSSM-500N Forsentek Co.) and a rotary magnetic encoder (i.e., RM08 RENISAHW Co.) into the kinematics chain. Both sensors play an essential role to extract the necessary HMI forces and pose information, bypassing Bowden cable non-linearities for a more accurate understanding of the interaction between the user and the device.

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Fig. 1. the Hand Exoskeleton on the right, the Remote Actuation System on the left.

B. RAS overview

Each finger is supposed to be driven independently. Therefore, the RAS was designed to house the electronics required to power and manage three motors, each of which is in charge of controlling a specific finger. The design was approached to ensure a maximum force of 15 N at the end-effector and the reversibility of the system; a highly desirable feature for devices that actively interact with the human body. Indeed, a mechanically reversible device has many advantages: high efficiency and, therefore, contained power losses in the transmission chain; a simplified wearing phase that can be performed with the motors off; the possibility to detect the user's interaction from any point of the mechanism by force sensors; a safe emergency-handling as the device can be always forced by the user in case of malfunctioning.

The scheme adopted involves using a brushless rotary electric motor (the HT1225 from *Haitai Mechanical and Electrical Equipment Co.*), capable of providing sufficiently high torque at a low number of revolutions without any reduction stages; an essential feature in terms of reversibility.

The motor's output is connected to a custom capstan to ensure a suitable housing for the cable tensioning pegs.

The diameter of the capstan has been designed four times larger than the pulley located on the HE to realize a multiplier for the direct drive and a reducer for backward motion, aiming to amplify the backdrivability of the system.

The electric/electronic scheme of each RAM, shown in Figure 1, involves transforming the 220V-AC input voltage into a constant 24V-supply voltage using an integrated switching power supply (HRPG-1000-24 by *Mean Well*).

The Nucleo development board (STM32F767ZI by *STMicroelectronics*), equipped with a 32-bit ARM processor, represents the central control unit of the whole system. It runs the algorithm that coordinates and supervises the other peripherals. It is, then, in charge of the high-level control of the system and, according to the type of control to perform (e.g., position-based, velocity-based, current-based), it monitors the status of

the exoskeleton and makes real-time decisions on the motor commands. The Sparkfun interface board (AST-CAN485 by *SparkFun Electronics*) samples and processes the analog signals coming from the load cell and the exoskeleton encoder, it receives high-level commands from the Nucleo board through I2C communication, and sends medium/low-level commands to the motor driver through an RS-485 serial protocol. The motor driver (the model HTPTZ by *Haitai Mechanical and Electrical Equipment Co.*) contains the firmware to drive the motor. A proprietary communication protocol allows the monitoring of various parameters, including current consumption, supply voltage, rpm, and absolute position.

CONCLUSION

The development and electromechanical design of a kinaesthetic hand exoskeleton prototype for rendering grasping and manipulation stimuli have been presented. According to the recent trends in literature, the proposed device is intended as a means of immersive interaction with virtual reality environments. The potential applications of such technology are multiple, but the ones closest to the adopted design philosophy are VR-based rehabilitation and physical training.

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